

CAUSES, CONSEQUENCES AND IMPACTS OF THE SEVERE G-4 GEOMAGNETIC STORM OF AUGUST 12, 2024**Sushant Pandey¹**

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ABSTRACT

On August 12, 2024, a severe geomagnetic storm reached its peak, categorized as G4 (severe) on the NOAA geomagnetic storm scale. This storm, driven by a series of Coronal Mass Ejections (CMEs), impacted satellite systems, communication networks, and resulted in visible auroras as far south as the southern United States. This paper examines the causes, consequences and impacts of the storm, providing an analysis based on real-time data, and placing the event within the context of Solar Cycle 25. In this paper effects of geomagnetic storm on the Earth magnetic field has been investigated by taking Dst-index, Kp index and AE index. The observed perturbation in the Earth magnetic field affects the communication, navigation and other technological system system via perturbing the electron density distribution of the ionosphere.

Keywords:

Geomagnetic Storm, Coronal mass ejection, Solar cycle, Auroras

INTRODUCTION

Geomagnetic storms happen when energy and particles from the Sun, especially during solar eruptions called coronal mass ejections (CMEs), hit Earth's magnetic field, causing disturbances. (NOAA SWPC, 2024). One of the strongest in recent years occurred on August 12, 2024, showing how such storms can affect our technology.

The storm began when solar particles reached Earth, interacting with the planet's magnetic field (ACE/DSCOVR DATA, 2024). The strength of this interaction depends on the direction of the interplanetary magnetic field (IMF) that comes with the solar wind. If the IMF points southward, it clashes more strongly with Earth's magnetic field (Knipp, 2011). During this storm, the IMF pointed south, leading to a powerful geomagnetic storm (Kivelson & Russell, 1995). We can measure the intensity of such storms using indices like the Kp and Dst, which both showed sharp increases during this event (GFZ, 2024).

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The storm disrupted satellites, especially those in geosynchronous orbits. These satellites are critical for communication and weather monitoring, but the storm induced currents in their systems, causing malfunctions. Many satellite operators reported communication issues, and radio signals used for aviation and ships in polar regions were also knocked out (NOAA SWPC Report, 2024).

In addition to satellite problems, the storm posed a risk to power grids. Geomagnetic storms can cause currents to flow through power lines, potentially damaging transformers and other equipment (Pulkkinen et al., 2017). While there were no major blackouts, power companies took precautions by changing how the grid was configured to reduce risk (EPRI, 2024).

This event highlights how dependent modern life is on technology that can be vulnerable to space weather. By studying data from storms like this one, scientists can better understand and predict future events, helping to protect satellites, communication systems, and power grids from serious damage (Tsurutani et al., 2006).

Solar Cycle 25, which began in 2019, has seen an increase in solar activity since 2023, characterized by more frequent CMEs and solar flares (NASA Heliophysics Division, 2023). Between August 8 and 10, 2024, five CMEs were observed leaving the Sun, heading toward Earth (Solar and Heliospheric Observatory, 2024). These CMEs interacted with Earth's magnetosphere, causing a series of geomagnetic disturbances leading up to the severe G4 storm on August 12.

The build-up of CMEs reaching Earth from August 11 into August 12 was a precursor to the storm. Solar Cycle 25, having reached its solar maximum phase, contributed to the heightened frequency of solar events, as evidenced by elevated sunspot numbers and flare activity (Solar Cycle Science Data Centre, 2024).

The August 12 geomagnetic storm was driven by a series of CMEs started between 8-10 Aug 2024 with solar wind speeds exceeding 600 km/s (ACE/DSCOVR Data, 2024). These CMEs carried a negative (southward) Bz component of the interplanetary magnetic field, allowing the solar wind to more effectively connect with Earth's magnetic field and inject energy into the magnetosphere (Kivelson & Russell, 1995).

Data from the ACE and DSCOVR spacecraft indicated that the solar wind plasma had an increased density, combined with enhanced magnetic field strength. The Bz component consistently stayed southward at -13nT to -17nT, a key parameter for strong geomagnetic storms, which enables the coupling between the solar wind and Earth's magnetic field (NASA GSFC, 2024).

COMPARISON WITH PREVIOUS GEOMAGNETIC STORMS

The August 12, 2024 storm, though severe, was less intense than the May 2024 storm, which reached G5 (extreme) on the NOAA scale (GFZ, 2024). For historical comparison, the August 2024 storm was far weaker than the infamous Carrington Event of 1859, which remains the most powerful geomagnetic storm on record with a Dst index approximated at -900 nT (Green & Boardsen, 2006).

Additionally, the March 1989 geomagnetic storm that caused a blackout in Québec had a similar Dst index to the August 2024 storm, but resulted in more significant infrastructure damage due to the vulnerabilities in the power grid at that time (Bolduc, 2002). Advances in monitoring and grid resilience have mitigated similar risks today (EPRI, 2024).

DATA USED AND VARIATIONS IN DST AND KP INDEX

The Kp index, which measures geomagnetic activity on a scale of 0 to 9, reached 8 during the peak of the storm, indicating severe geomagnetic activity. The Disturbance Storm Time (Dst) index (WDC for Geomagnetism, Kyoto), which measures the ring current's intensity and represents the overall impact on the Earth's magnetic field, reached -188 nT during the peak.

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By comparison, the May 2024 storm, one of the most intense in Solar Cycle 25, had a Dst index of -412 nT. Though the August 12 storm was less intense than the May event, it still caused widespread technological impacts. There are plots of Kp index of 11-14 Aug 2024 (GFZ German Research Centre for Geosciences) and plot of DST index in nT for 11-14 Aug 2024 as follows –

Plot of Dst index from 11-14 Aug 2024

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

One of the most immediate concerns during the geomagnetic storm was the increased drag on low-Earth orbit (LEO) satellites. The storm caused a significant expansion of Earth's atmosphere, increasing the density at higher altitudes. This effect led to heightened drag on satellites, which required orbital adjustments to maintain proper positioning. As noted in the Space Weather Prediction Center (SWPC) warnings, satellite operators were advised of potential increased fuel consumption for altitude corrections (SWPC Alerts, 2024).

High-frequency (HF) radio communication was heavily impacted by the storm, particularly in polar regions. The NOAA Space Weather Prediction Center reported HF radio blackouts at high latitudes due to increased ionospheric absorption. This affected aviation and marine industries that rely on HF communications, particularly for trans-polar flights (ICAO Guidance, 2024).

While no major power outages were reported during the event, G4-class storms pose significant risks to power grid infrastructures, particularly in high-latitude areas such as Canada, northern Europe, and the northern United States. The G4 classification is associated with potential voltage instability and transformer damage due to geomagnetically induced currents (GICs) (EPRI, 2024).

One of the more visible consequences of the storm was the widespread auroras observed across mid-latitude regions. The southward-pointing Bz component during the storm allowed auroras to be seen as far south as Texas and Arizona, a rare occurrence for such low latitudes. These auroras were reported in both the northern and southern hemispheres, providing a spectacular display due to the strength of the storm.

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Images of Auroral activity at Arizona and Texas respectively.

<https://www.azfamily.com/2024/08/12/look-up-northern-lights-meteor-shower-could-be-visible-across-arizona-tonight/>

<https://www.chron.com/news/space/article/northern-lights-texas-19651596.php>

CONCLUSION

The geomagnetic storm of August 12, 2024, underscores the importance of understanding space weather phenomena and preparing for their potential impacts on modern technology. Although this storm did not result in catastrophic failures, it disrupted critical systems, such as satellite communications and HF radio, and highlighted the vulnerabilities of power grids.

As Solar Cycle 25 progresses, the likelihood of similar or more severe storms remains high. Continued improvements in space weather monitoring and forecasting will be essential to mitigate the risks posed by future geomagnetic storms. This paper provides an in-depth study of the August 12, 2024 geomagnetic storm, leveraging real-time data and placing the event within a historical context. Further studies should focus on how predictive models can improve early warning systems for geomagnetic storms, especially as solar activity continues to increase.

REFERENCES

1. Bolduc, L. (2002). GIC observations and studies in the Hydro-Québec power system. *Journal of Atmospheric and Solar-Terrestrial Physics*, 64(16), 1793–1802.
2. EPRI (Electric Power Research Institute). (2024). *Geomagnetic Storm Risk and Power Grid Mitigation Strategies*. Retrieved from EPRI Reports.
3. GFZ German Research Centre for Geosciences. (2024). *Kp Index Data for Geomagnetic Activity*, 11–14 August 2024.
4. Green, J. L., & Boardsen, S. (2006). Commentary: The Carrington Event of 1859 – A Modern Perspective. *Advances in Space Research*, 38(2), 213–222.

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Published By:

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5. ICAO (International Civil Aviation Organization). (2024). Guidance on HF Communication for Polar Routes During Geomagnetic Storms.
6. Kivelson, M. G., & Russell, C. T. (1995). Introduction to Space Physics. Cambridge University Press.
7. Knipp, D. J. (2011). Understanding Space Weather and the Physics Behind It. McGraw-Hill.
8. NASA GSFC (Goddard Space Flight Center). (2024). Solar Wind Parameters from DSCOVR Data.
9. NASA Heliophysics Division. (2023). Solar Cycle 25 Observations and Predictions. Retrieved from NASA Heliophysics Website.
10. NOAA Space Weather Prediction Center (SWPC). (2024). Alerts and Reports on August 2024 Geomagnetic Storm.
11. Pulkkinen, A., Bernabeu, E., Eichner, J., et al. (2017). Geoelectric Hazard Maps for the Continental US. Space Weather, 15(2), 212–227.
12. Solar and Heliospheric Observatory (SOHO). (2024). CME Observations, 8–10 August 2024.
13. Solar Cycle Science Data Center. (2024). Solar Maximum and CME Frequencies During Solar Cycle 25.
14. Tsurutani, B. T., Gonzalez, W. D., & Lakhina, G. S. (2006). The Extreme Magnetic Storm of November 20, 2003. Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics, 111(A7).